

Enhancement of Conflict Resolution Skill and Communication Skill through a Peace Education Program.

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ABSTRACT

This study mainly aimed to enhance Conflict Resolution skill and Communication skill through the Peace Education Program. A mixed method was utilized for the present study. Pre-test and Post-test quasi-experimental designs were used and 62 students were randomly chosen as the sample for the present study. Peace Education Program Session included cooperative activity for conflict resolution, a film, a documentary on human rights, justice and peace, a case study activity for problem-solving and group discussion for understanding peace level and identifying the conflicts, implemented for the experimental group. Conflict resolution skill and communication skill scales have been applied for the pre-test and post-test groups. Data analysis statistical test found that the Peace Education Program had significantly enhanced Conflict Resolution skill and Communication skill.

Keywords: conflict resolution skill, communication skill and peace education

INTRODUCTION

OUR CONSTITUENT ASSEMBLY, on this twenty-sixth day of November, 1949, do hereby adopt, enact, and give to ourselves this Constitution. WE, THE PEOPLE OF INDIA, having solemnly resolved to constitute India into an SOVEREIGN SOCIALIST SECULAR DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC, and to secure to all its citizens: JUSTICE, social, economic, and political; LIBERTY of thought, expression, belief, faith, and worship; EQUALITY of status and of opportunity; and to promote among them all FRATERNITY, assuring the dignity of the individual and the unity and integrity of the nation.

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar said that the Constitution was workable, flexible, and strong enough to hold the country together both in peacetime and wartime."In fact, if I may say so, if things go wrong under the new Constitution, it will not be because we had a bad Constitution." What we must claim is that Man was evil." Internal value is achieved by applying directive ideals such as justice, liberty, equality, and brotherhood.

For peace and sustainability, the youth of India need to be endorsed and follow the path of Vidhya- Knowledge, Pradnaya- Wisdom, Karuna- Compassion, Sheel-Character, and Maitree- Friendship, propounded by Lord Buddha.

"Peace comes from within. Do not seek it without."- Buddha.

To achieve peace within a person, the Buddhist approach is to observe and reflect upon the conditions in the external and mental operations and then decide on the most appropriate course of action to respond to the outer and inner environments.

“The ability to think clearly, the ability to perform well in the workplace, and the ability to value life are the fruits of education.” Says Mahatma Jyoti Rao Phule.

Knowledge is important because it has the power to challenge, change, and transform individuals and societies. Education has the potential to empower people and make society more democratic.

You should carefully guard your mind, maintaining mindfulness all the time in order to cease conflicts. (The Middle Length Discourses of the Buddha, Taisho 1: 26).

This is the foundation for the Buddha’s followers to live in peace since peace depends more on how individuals perceive and react to their circumstances than on the events themselves. The insight (vipassana) we gain from introspection in the context of the dependent origination principle is the only way to comprehend the intricate web of multiple forces, causes, and conditions that have shaped the event and our immediate perception of, feelings toward, and response to it.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

In 2017 Maurya, Ram Shiromani conducted a study on Conflict Resolution of Secondary School Students through peace education. To study the effect of peace education on Conflict Resolution powers of secondary school students. Method of the research mixed approach on 40 students of the 11th class. A researcher has found that the mean difference between the pre-test and post-test scores was found significant for the dimensions such as truth, love, non-violence, and compassion resulting in the peaceful conflict resolution of the students for these dimensions. While the mean difference between the pre and post-test scores was not found significant for the dimension related to religion as pacts and work is worship. **In 2012 Singh and Vikramajit** focused on the Effect of peace education strategies on the development of conflict resolution skills among adolescent students. And researcher has found significant merit in the development of dimension-wise as well as factor-wise Conflict resolution skills (CRS) among adolescent students. development of attitude towards conflict resolution (ATCR) among adolescent students. development of dimension-wise attitude towards conflict resolution (ATCR) among adolescent students. Through Peace education strategy. Also, the researcher has found no significant effect on sex or class in terms of developing conflict resolution skills among adolescent students and no significant effect on sex or class in terms of developing attitudes towards conflict resolution (ATCR) among adolescent students through the Peace education strategy.

In 2021 Sekerci, Hanifi; Yilmaz and Ferat conducted a study on The Role of Respectful Behaviour in the Relationship between Empathetic Tendencies and Conflict Resolution in Primary School Students’ Purpose. Empathetic inclination and conflict resolution skills were

shown to be significantly correlated, with empathetic tendency accounting for 36% of the variance in conflict resolution skills. As also suggested in the research hypotheses, in addition to the existence of a relationship between an empathetic tendency and conflict resolution skills through a model in which respectful behaviour is a significant partial mediator, the empathetic tendency can explain conflict resolution skills at a level of 54%. Implications for Research and Practice: In future research, it should be investigated, which skill, value, demographic information, etc. Other than empathetic tendencies and respectful behavior, the perplexing variance ratio could be explained. **In 2018 Ismet Arýcý** researcher focused on the ability to communicate strongly in the mental, emotional, and behavioral areas plays an important role in providing students with knowledge and skills. Researcher has examined whether the communication skills of the students differ according to their gender, class, and education field variables results showed that the communication skills of the students did not differ according to their gender, class, and education fields. When the research findings are evaluated, it is clear that the communication abilities of the teacher candidates in the Fine Arts Department's Music and Arts education branches are at a high level in terms of mental, emotional, and behavioral elements.

NEED AND RATIONALE OF THE STUDY:

It is necessary to read articles related to research problems because it ignites the researcher's mind. From such literature, researcher gets guidance and inspiration. From such literature researcher taught that were fewer studies conducted on degree college students' enhancement in conflict resolution skill and communication skill through the peace education program.

From the research conducted in India and Abroad researcher came to know that conflict Resolution is correlated with peace Building imperatives for religious leaders and school attachment aggression. Communication skill related to, interpersonal skills of quality of care, self-efficacy, and job satisfaction at different levels. Peace Education programs correlate beyond Ethnocentrism and violence, caring skill, and Emotional Intelligence. The researcher comes to know about this when the researcher related the literature of the research. The researcher came to know that less research is conducted on this topic on students studying at different levels and different strategies used at the college level. it is most to important to investigate and understand how different strategies can be more widely adopted and effectively used by students in order to equip the students with knowledge and understanding for peaceful relationships and help to promote the development of attitudes and a wide range of skills that help to students cope effectively with the challenges of everyday life and make more good communication skill or conflict-free life. Hence there is a need to conduct this research.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To develop a peace education program for enhancing the conflict resolution skill and communication skill of degree college female students.
2. To implement the peace education program.
3. To study and compare the pre-test scores of the control group and experimental group of

conflict resolution skill and communication skill among degree college students.

4. To study and compare the post-test scores of control group and experimental group of conflict resolution skill and communication skill among degree college students.

5. To study the effect of peace education program among degree college students.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY:

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of the control group and experimental group for enhancement of Conflict Resolution skill among degree college students with respect to the following dimensions.

A] Aggressive Behaviour

B] Problem-Solving

2. There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of the control group and experimental group for enhancement of Communication skill among degree college students with respect to the following dimensions.

A] Cognitive

B] Emotion

C] Behaviour

3. There is no significant difference in the post-test scores of the control group and experimental group for enhancement of Conflict Resolution skill among degree college students with respect to the following dimensions.

A] Aggressive Behaviour

B] Problem-Solving

4. There is no significant difference in post-test scores of the control group and experimental group for enhancement of Communication skill among degree college students with respect to the following dimensions.

A] Cognitive

B] Emotion

C] Behaviour

METHODOLOGY:

Method of the research was mixed approach as both qualitative and quantitative methods has been used in the study.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE FOR THE STUDY:

The population for the present study consists of degree college students. Students from F.Y. (First Year) B.Com. for 31 control group students and 31 total no. of students 62 and for the pilot study 75 students from 4 degree college students were selected through random sampling technique for the study.

TOOLS USED FOR THE STUDY:

In this study, the researcher herself prepared the five-point Likert scale to determine

Conflict Resolution skill and the scale of Communication skill was administered to both groups to examine the enhancement of Conflict Resolution skill and Communication skill among degree college students. It consists of two sub-scales: Aggressive Behaviour and Problem-Solving scale in terms of Conflict Resolution. The reliability coefficient was calculated, Cronbach's Alpha Validity to be 0.96 for 62 items'. The scale of Communication Skill the reliability coefficient was calculated Cronbach's Alpha Validity to be 0.86 for 50 items'

DATA ANALYSIS:

To evaluate the raw data, percentage analysis, mean, standard deviation, and the t-test were used.

PRE CONTROL AND EXPERIMENTS TEST					
	GROUP	MEAN	SD	T-RATIO	SIGNIFICANCE
Conflict Resolution skill	CONTROL	238.387096 8	38.4982 1	1.6522	<i>not</i> significant at $p < 0.05$.
	EXPERIMENTAL	225.741	18.2581 3		
Communication skill	CONTROL	178.774	28.1409 7	0.07503 3	<i>not</i> significant at $p < 0.05$.
	EXPERIMENTAL	178.322	18.2581 3		
Aggressive	CONTROL	124.0322	18.0175	1.088	<i>not</i> significant at $p < 0.05$.
	EXPERIMENTAL	118.258	12.6173 6		
Problem Solving	CONTROL	114.419	22.176	1.3671	<i>not</i> significant at $p < 0.05$
	EXPERIMENTAL	107.483	17.498		
Cognitive	CONTROL	59.87096	9.999	-0.869	<i>not</i> significant at $p < 0.05$
	EXPERIMENTAL	61.8064	7.6263		
Emotional	CONTROL	59.41935	9.2006	47.196	<i>not</i> significant at $p < 0.05$
	EXPERIMENTAL	63.4838	6.5973		
Behaviour	CONTROL	59.48387	11.0479 9	2.8262	<i>not</i> significant at $p < 0.05$
	EXPERIMENTAL	53.03225	7.1623		

Table: 1 There is no significant difference in the pre-test in the control and experiment group with respect to dimensions of Conflict Resolution and Communication skill. Experimental and control group in two sub-scales of Conflict Resolution (Aggression and Problem-Solving) in pre-test there is no significant difference between the experimental and control group at the t - value of (0.05) level .

POST CONTROL AND EXPIRIMENT TEST					
	GROUP	MEAN	SD	T - RATIO	SIGNIFICANCE
Conflict Resolution skill	CONTROL	178.483 9	21.1358	6.1697	significant at $p < 0.05$.
	EXPERIMENTAL	222.322 7	33.4428		
Communication skill	CONTROL	237.096 8	27.2706 9	13.532 1	significant at $p < 0.05$.
	EXPERIMENTAL	169.548 4	18.9786 5		
Aggressive	CONTROL	121.645 2	15.081	0.3427	not significant at $p < 0.05$.
	EXPERIMENTAL	116.096 8	16.563		
Problem Solving	CONTROL	115.451 6	14.3407 1	2.0939 6	significant at $p < 0.05$.
	EXPERIMENTAL	106.225 8	19.9042 9		
Cognitive	CONTROL	62.645	9.307	1.6725 6	not significant at $p < 0.05$.
	EXPERIMENTAL	58.806	8.757		
Emotional	CONTROL	62.0645	7.261	1.965	significant at $p < 0.05$.
	EXPERIMENTAL	58.677	6.231		
Behaviour	CONTROL	53.774	7.77	0.9144	not significant at $p < 0.05$.
	EXPERIMENTAL	52.064	6.97		

Table: 2 After completion of the PEP(Peace Education Program), the researcher observed that there is a significant difference in the control and experimental group in the Conflict Resolution skill scale at the level of $p < 0.05$ t - ratio 6.1697. The mean difference is higher for the experimental group($x=222.322$) null hypothesis is rejected. Researcher found a significant difference in Communication skill 13.5321. The mean difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x= 237.09$ and experimental mean is $x = 169.54$). Researcher found not significant difference for the Aggressive sub-scale ($x = 116.0968$) at the level of $p < 0.05$ t - ratio is 0.3427. The mean difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x= 121.6452$ and experimental mean is $x = 116.0968$) null hypothesis is accepted. Researcher observed Problem-Solving sub-scale at the level of $p < 0.05$ t- ratio is 2.09396. The mean difference is higher for the experimental group ($x = 106.2258$) null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, these results show that participants in the PEP enhance Conflict Resolution skill. The researcher also found that the Cognitive dimension not significant difference in control group and experimental group at the level of $p < 0.05$ t - ratio is 1.6725. The mean difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x=62.0645$ and experimental mean is $x = 58.677$) null hypothesis accepted . researcher found the emotional dimension a significant difference in the control and experimental group at the level of $p < 0.05$ t - ratio is 1.965.the mean difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x=62.0645$ and experimental mean is $x = 58.677$) null hypothesis rejected. The researcher found that the Behaviour dimension not significant difference in control group and experimental group at the level of $p < 0.05$ t - ratio is 0.9144. The mean difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x=53.774$ and experimental mean is $x = 52.064$) null hypothesis accepted . Researcher observed that the mean difference with the dimensions of Aggressive, Problem Solving, Cognitive , Emotional, Behaviour is show higher for control group and lower for the experimental group. Researcher found that the students gave exam of first sem and after that exam they field the scale and its may be difficult to cope and may be impact of stress on their proper cognition to select response of their natural behavior.

DISCUSSION:

From this research, the researcher observed that at the global level, peace is important for the development of individuals and nations wise also and for the creation of a better foundation and root for the future generation. This type of program can impact effectively enhance and maintain inner peace and understand the cause of conflict and rectify the problem with the calm and care its needs to integrate this kind of education into school, college for a better foundation. The researcher also found through the hypothesis of Conflict Resolution skills significant difference shows between the control and experimental group. It shows peace education care, empathy, anger, fighting, and bullying factors students understand the problem roots and collaboration and co-operative how it's needed to manage they explore through the PEP program.

QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS:

The researcher through the peace education program uses open-ended types of Question through the different Activity which lead to understanding the concept of conflict, understanding the root of conflict, and resolving with peaceful solutions its shows how controlled anger in a conflict situation and show empathy, care, stop bullying and fighting with the cooperation with the compromise, avoid and how justice these factors lead resolve conflict and enhance communication skill through peace education among youth.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

This study dealt with First-year degree college students in the commerce field from thane district college. This study was limited to college students aged 18 to 25 years. Does not include other colleges from the other district and cities.

THE DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUE IS REPRESENTED IN THE DIAGRAM:

Data – Code - Category — Theme – Context.

From the different activities, the researcher found code as conflict words, feelings, emotions, value, status, and power these leads category and main category individual and social structure related to behaviour and attitude pattern. Also, the category related to Emotion, Empathy. And Themes related to the meaning of conflict resolution, conflict culture, peace values, disparity, human rights, and conflict-resolving methods. Context-related social inter group conflict.

Activity	Code	Category	Theme	Context
1 1 session 2 sessions	Conflict, feeling, emotion, different opinions of people, different values of people. Adjustment, management of things or timing and sharing the device, Conflict arouses due to values accepted by parents and students' perception (conflict values and cultural pattern), Expressing a point of view in front of parents and parents had faith in the child given the opportunity to succeed and parents fill proud of the child's success - solving the problem with right/good discussion (convince with good communication). Understanding feeling each other and resolving the problem	The Behaviour of Humans and Emotions, cognition relate to maintain peace	Individual Social	Identification of Conflict meaning of Conflict. (Dysfunctional Conflict)
2	Avoid others teasing, ignoring, and misbehaving either ignore or try to sort it out, inform the teacher or principal, or help others. Taking the help of others (teachers), try to convince them.	Aggressive behaviour, skill of Emotional Balance to sustain peace	Individual Social	Root of conflict (violence, Discrimination) manage behaviour for better Communication

3	Cast, religion, and gender discrimination factors seen in society (social intro conflict). women tried to fight for their husband’s justice (Human Rights, Violence) Understand other humans. like how in the movie, exactly, a woman was fighting for her right. human rights mean freedom, the social value that because of our freedom, every person has an equal chance to live.	Dignity , Right for justice and Respect	Individual Social	Inter group conflict caste system) Human rights
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DISCUSSION:

Through these activities, the researcher has recognized the youth’s viewpoints about the conflict’s meaning and how to solve it peacefully. As per the information, the researcher understands that students give their opinion about conflict like conflict meaning feeling, Emotion, value affection, dispute, happiness, and status and finally, they construct the definition of conflict it is a fight between two different feelings or values among people. The researcher found from the students’ responses to the peace education activity that the conflict appears as such When giving a critical opinion about this concept, according to him conflict is a fight between two different feelings for values among people meaning is explained before with the help of his thoughts they combine the same definitions with the help of ritual words such as feeling emotions value affect happiness status the researcher finds out from the response of the students. It comes that the attitude of human beings is the power they have. Also, conflict is a difference of opinion. Differences also have an impact on social interaction from an individual view. Research has found what reality students perceive through pictures and the response of students when asked to correlate it with real life. Student’s response to the statement ‘they are motivated to explore or try to solve the problem here researcher observe behaviour pattern with context with love and care researcher felt that this behaviour pattern related to Eric Erickson in 1966-68 Erickson stated that development usually happens during young adulthood, which is between the ages of 18 and 40. This stage marks a transition from just thinking about ourselves to thinking about other people in the world. With the response of students, they will understand the situation sometimes they comprise and neglect without reacting to bully person and stranger’s researcher observe students understand the proper gesture of communicating with a proper emotional set of minds. The researcher also observes from the response of respondents a statement of ‘human rights mean freedom, the social value that because of our freedom, every person has an equal chance to live.’ Here researchers observe social inter conflict cast and class and race systems this structure of society ultimately the effect of social structure on human behaviour. Researchers observed from the student’s response cast structure and classification impact on individual and social life here researcher observes behaviour and communication skill pattern attitude development it relates to Karl Marks social theory Karl Marks stated that capitalist societies were built on conflicts between the workers and the rulers. In this theory, society relies on class conflict in order to keep the wealthy in power and the poor as subjects to the government. The researcher also observes from the student’s response or statement ‘Women tried to fight for her husband’s justice (Human Rights, Violence) Understand other humans. like how in the

movie, exactly, a woman was fighting for her right. human rights mean freedom, the social value that because of our freedom, every person has an equal chance to live.’ Here researcher observes for the individual and social equal opportunity nation must need a good foundation or principal for peace and the student’s response reflects that equal opportunity maintains peace and healthy life. In the Indian context, our constitution is our foundation of life. ‘Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar said that the Constitution was workable, flexible, and strong enough to hold the country together both in peacetime and in war time’.

CONCLUSION:

Here the students have clearly stated that the conflict as arguing, blaming, different feelings or values among people. individuals, social resources, power-related, behavior, and attitude-related behavior etc. All these are feeling, emotion and thought firstly increase in human mind and here with the help students response and involvement of activity they shown their behaviour in any conflict, which they face that’s lead to reduce anger and fighting attitude try to control their emotion and build their relationship with calm behaviour and came out the situation. This activity also help the students understand the actual meaning of conflict and its also help students to understand their feelings and expiration. Student engagement was wonderful, and from their experience, the researcher gained more knowledge about the facts. What exactly do they think about the conflict? Through this activity, researchers learn how to manage things. How can we conduct our activities more effectively? Also, regarding their syllabus components, how can researchers add more things? The researcher was very excited to collaborate with this level of students so they could do more things for them. The researcher felt confident. As students enjoyed the activity. During this activity researcher learn about the management. Researcher observe that girls participants where hesitated to reflect of bullying. Also, the researcher observes that the participants had good level of ability work in a team. social inter group - conflict impact on the individual and social life of human its reflect from the responses. with the understanding the structure of cast, religion, race, sex this aspect of society structure distinguish human behaviour and attitude. Its lead to reflect human behaviour towards their self and society this pattern of communication enhance their skill. After this activity, the researcher observed changes of the behaviour of the students. Researcher also realized that watching films and analyzing enhance students understanding.

This study can enhance the ability of conflict resolution and communication skill through peace education programs. This study enlightens youth and makes a strong foundation through peace education. It builds a relationship with care and empathy that is lead the peaceful mind of individual and society in a healthy manner. This study dealt with social inter conflicts like social exclusion, caste, and women’s economic status. They understand society’s structure and root of conflict and resolve it well manner and develop their communication skill with Cognitive, Emotional, and behaviour patterns.

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